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THE IMPACT OF THE RUSSIAN-UKRAINIAN WAR ON THE DYNAMICS OF MOLDOVA'S EUROPEAN INTEGRATION COURSE

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Abstract

The article examines the changes in the dynamics of the European Integration course of the Republic of Moldova under the influence of the Russian-Ukrainian war. It provides forecasts regarding the further pro-European direction of the Republic of Moldova, given the prevention of destabilizing scenarios by Russia on Moldovan territory. The article also emphasizes the significance for the Republic of Moldova to become a member of the European Union, particularly in the context of the Russian-Ukrainian war.

Keywords: *European Integration, Russian-Ukrainian War, Moldova`s pro-european direction, Transnistria, Moldova`s security*

The experience of European integration for the Republic of Moldova in the conditions of the war in the neighboring state of Ukraine is both unique and contradictory. Despite the crisis of internal political and economic processes and the inflow of 4.8 million refugees (European Council, 2023) caused by the full-scale Russian invasion of Ukraine, attempts of destabilization, and diversions in the territory of the unrecognized Transnistria (Vitalie Călugăreanu, 2022), the country has still obtained the status of a candidate for EU membership. It continues to implement European integration reforms and fulfill the provisions of the Association Agreement and European Commission recommendations (European Council, 2022).

It should be noted that the ongoing phase of European integration processes in the Republic of Moldova and Ukraine is primarily influenced by the military threat from Russia towards the territorial integrity of both Ukraine and Moldova. Additionally, it is affected by the unpredictability of global political and economic processes, the existence of crises within the EU resulting from the Russian military aggression against Ukraine, and internal problems within the country. Some of these factors are influenced by the activities of pro-Russian ideological political forces in Moldova, which have not yet recognized Russia as an aggressor and continue their activities in the Parliament of the Republic of Moldova. This poses a direct threat to the country and its European future, which, according to the WatchDog survey

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supported by the European Union, is supported by 51.9% of Moldovan citizens as of March 2023 (WatchDog Survey, 2023). It is worth noting that the year of the Russian-Ukrainian war has already impacted Moldova's European integration course in various aspects, including security, economic, and political aspects.

Pro-European Vector of Moldova: The Impact of the Russian-Ukrainian War

The war in Russia against Ukraine has significantly influenced the European integration processes, primarily for Ukraine, whose government submitted its application for EU membership on February 28, followed by Moldova's acting president signing a corresponding application on March 3. Later, on June 23, 2022, a historical event occurred as both countries were granted the status of candidate countries during the EU summit. Thus, it can be argued that the activation of European membership became the response of EU-associated countries to Russia's aggression in Ukraine. Even though EU accession does not entail NATO collective defense, it remains the only geopolitical alternative for Moldova's integration into the Western sphere to avoid becoming a potential gray area for Russian influence. Therefore, from the EU's perspective, there is a strategic sense in including Moldova as part of the European family.

In response to Moldova's application for EU accession, pro-Russian forces in the country attempted internal destabilization steps, calling for a referendum (Cristina Jicol, 2022), while Transnistria used this occasion to reaffirm its position regarding independence from Moldova (Ministry of Foreign Affairs of PMR, 2022).

However, immediately after obtaining the candidate status for the Republic of Moldova, a noticeable shift in discourse and the positions of other Moldovan politicians began. Initially, during the full-scale Russian war against Ukraine, Moldova maintained a cautious stance regarding the approval of EU sanctions against the Russian Federation, citing the complexity of imposing sanctions, particularly concerning the protection of Moldova's economy, which had suffered significantly due to the pandemic, energy, and economic crises (Vitalie Călugăreanu, 2022). But within a year after the full-scale invasion, with the change in Moldova's government led by the new Prime Minister Dorin Rechany, the Moldovan authorities demonstrated a clear change in rhetoric from "our country stands for peace" to "we condemn the war in Ukraine initiated by Russia."

It is worth mentioning that the current Prime Minister is a former advisor to Maia Sandu on defense and national security matters.

An illustrative point is that after Moldova was granted candidate country status for EU accession, it will join the EU in adopting further sanctions against Russia, showing solidarity with Ukraine. As a candidate state, Moldova is expected to align with the EU on such decisions.

The future pro-European direction of Moldova: prospects

Despite the noticeable progress in various areas of the Republic of Moldova as identified by the European Commission, the realization of all tasks and EU recommendations still requires efforts from both the government and Moldovan society. According to the decision of the European Council, Moldova must undertake various tasks related to justice reform, electoral system, fighting corruption, de-oligarchization, combating organized crime and money laundering, improving public services, reforming state governance and public finances, among others (European Commission, 2023).

In the priorities announced by the newly appointed Prime Minister Dorin Rechan (Moldpress, 2023), which relate to economic development, restoring order and discipline in state institutions, and ensuring peace and stability, European integration also holds a prominent place. The ability to carry out reforms associated with this process will play a crucial role in determining the success of the new government and the implementation of its agenda. The progress in the justice sector will have a ripple effect on all other areas, as reflected in the European Commission's recommendations in the context of candidate country status for EU accession.

In the past year, 2022, the current pro-European government fulfilled only half of the actions it was supposed to accomplish by the end of that year. However, in January 2023, during a meeting of the National Commission on Eurointegration, President Maia Sandu called on all state institutions to expedite the implementation of the remaining actions by June 2023. The goal is to complete all nine conditions set by the European Commission, after which negotiations for accession can begin. It is noteworthy that the deadline was set by Chisinau, not Brussels, indicating Moldova's keen interest in fulfilling all the recommendations for the next step towards EU accession.

According to statements by the Minister of Foreign Affairs and European Integration, Nicu Popescu, in 2023, Moldova's government will also focus on applying sanctions to fugitive oligarchs to prevent destabilization by criminal groups. On April 28, the EU Council adopted a decision to apply restrictive measures to individuals involved in actions that destabilize Moldova, threaten its sovereignty and independence, and undermine the rule of law and stability. Restrictive measures may also be applied to individuals involved in embezzlement of state funds, those who can take control of or significantly influence the activities of state institutions (European Council, 2023).

The determination to fulfill the EU's requirements and implement measures to counteract destabilizing influences demonstrates Moldova's commitment to progressing towards EU integration. These efforts are crucial for Moldova's prospects and strengthening its position in the European family.

In the agenda for 2023, there is also the organization of the European Political Community Summit to support the common goal of a peaceful and stable Europe, which will take place on June 1 in Chisinau (the Ministry of Foreign Affairs and European Integration, 2023).

In summary, the Russian-Ukrainian war has significantly accelerated the European integration processes in the Republic of Moldova, particularly in terms of expediting the implementation of necessary pro-European reforms by Moldova itself, as well as increasing attention from Western partners.

This attention from European partners was motivated not only by Moldova's proximity to Ukraine, which is currently fighting for its sovereignty and serves as a strong defensive shield for both Moldova and European countries but also by the potential threats of destabilizing processes within Moldova and in the unrecognized Transnistria, emanating from pro-Russian political forces. In the event of a negative development scenario, Russia's influence on Moldovan territory would increase significantly, potentially opening another front that would inevitably impact the course of the Russo-Ukrainian war and the future peaceful coexistence in EU countries.

The granting of candidate status to Moldova for EU accession is a signal of support from Western partners. It is hoped that Moldova's new status as a candidate country for EU accession will mark the beginning of a new stage of cooperation in all necessary areas, with a particular focus on Moldova's security and defense with the EU.

Overall, the pro-European direction Moldova is taking, coupled with the support from Western partners, demonstrates the country's commitment to its European integration aspirations and the shared goal of a peaceful and stable Europe.

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